

Employee Morale and its Dimensions: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Employee morale continues to be a favorite area of research in the HR domain. As organizations are placing a heightened emphasis on human resources and human capital to achieve the organization's overall goals, the concept of moral occupies an important place in the HR ecosystem. The concept is a bit abstract, and defining it precisely and accurately has always been a tough ask. Nevertheless, researchers have contributed to the literature on employee morale, including its different dimensions. This paper reviews such literature that has dealt with employee morale and its different dimensions. Literature defining morale, explaining its importance, discussing the consequences and causes of low morale, and measures to avoid low morale has been reviewed in this paper.

Keywords: Employee morale, low morale, the importance of morale

INTRODUCTION

Employee morale is defined as the satisfaction, attitude, and overall outlook of employees during their association with a firm. An employee who is motivated and satisfied at the workplace generally tend to have higher morale than others. Employee satisfaction and employee engagement play a significant role for employees to be happy in their workplace. Employee morale is a dynamic concept. It is impacted by various factors that may change over time. The organization has to keep a continuous tab at the levels of employee morale and ensure that they are always healthy. The concept remains quite central to the HR domain, notwithstanding the passage of time. Hence this paper reviews such literature that has dealt with employee morale and its different dimensions. Literature defining morale, explaining its importance, discussing the consequences and causes of low morale, and measures to avoid low morale has been reviewed in this paper.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Morale

Morale has been defined differently by different authors. The researcher in this work considered definitions provided by two authors - Haddock and Seroka. These two authors have defined morale as an intangible concept, referring it to imply feelings of a group towards the organization to which they belong being positive and supportive, and the special feelings members of the group shared such as self-worth, trust, pride in oneself achievement, purpose, organizational success and faith in leadership. The definition also indicated the general level of optimism or confidence experienced by people or a group of people, particularly if it affects willingness and discipline (Haddock, 2010, Seroka 2009).

Morale is an attitude or the state of mind of an individual or group towards the work and environment, that is, towards the superior, colleagues, and goals of the organization and the task assigned. A favorable attitude indicates high morale, while an unfavorable attitude indicates low morale. An important factor contributing to people's willingness to work, leading to their happiness and determining their productivity, is morale. It is considered a major variable that determines the success of an organization. Armed with high morale, people work enthusiastically and willingly towards the achievement of organizational goals.

Further, high morale means that people attach greater significance to group goals instead of their personal goals. It also reduces labor turnover and absenteeism. On the other hand, low morale results in low productivity, waste, inefficiency, indiscipline, and unrest. Morale is closely related to self-respect, contributing to a positive self-image (Senge, 1990; Seroka, 2009; Haddock, 2010).

Morale is largely impacted from the top down (management) instead of bottom-up (first-line employees). It is difficult to consistently explain good or poor morale in terms of a single factor as its cause. Rather it is a mix of related factors, leading to poor or good morale (Finger, 2005). One can agree with Finger (2005) by extending that morale may be perceived as group behavior and as an individual matter. Also, the morale of individual members in a group impacts the group morale. These are the concepts that are the basis of morale in the organization and its relevance in the

organizational environment and its leadership. If morale is on the lower side, members' participation is likely to be limited in doing what is required or otherwise expected. Conversely, morale on the higher side suggests that individuals will participate with a sense of commitment and enthusiasm (Finger, 2005, David & Gary, 2010).

The importance of morale in the workplace

Morale is the fuel that drives an organization forward; or the fuel that feeds the fires of poor performance, employee discontent, and absenteeism (Ewton, 2007). Neely (1999) explored the relationship between productivity and morale and possible steps that a superior can take to improve employee morale. In the study, the results revealed a pattern that linked employees' productivity with their level of morale (Neely, 1999). Ewton (2007) emphasized the fact that employee morale is related to absenteeism, which has been reported to cost large businesses in the United States USD 0.76 million per annum in direct payroll costs, and even more when lost revenue, lower productivity, and other effects of low morale were considered. Low morale comes with a high price tag. The Gallup Organization (2007) estimated that there were 22 million actively disengaged employees costing the US economy as much as \$350 billion per annum in productivity that was lost, including absenteeism, illness, and other problems, all of which resulted in employees being unhappy at work, leading to low morale.

Millett (2010) mentioned six causes why staff morale was important. These were improved performance and creativity, improved productivity, higher attention to detail, reduced number of leave days, increased quality of work, and a safer workplace.

Consequences and causes of low morale

Low morale can have a negative effect on an organization's productivity. According to Dallas (2010) and Neely (1999), the following are the factors that are the effects of low morale at the workplace

High absenteeism

A higher incidence of workers not coming to work can have an adverse effect on workplace productivity.

Customer complaints

If the employees work with customers regularly and customers complain frequently, the effect could be negative, as the organization may lose many customers. Customers may cite instances of being treated indifferently or rudely or may complain about a lack of follow-up on a problem or question. This type of behavior results in dissatisfied customers and, eventually, a loss of business.

Poor attitude

If the employee is openly bitter or hostile, she or he can display a bad attitude. She/he may not participate actively during meetings or may be unwilling to help other employees. She/he may also exhibit a lack of enthusiasm towards her/his job and may somehow perform only the bare minimum duty required to maintain employment.

Poor work quality

Poor quality of work can negatively affect the organization, particularly from a worker who once was a top performer. The worker may have been bypassed over while promotion or is perhaps no more challenged by her/his job and has lost interest. In the case of newer employees, it could result from a lack of understanding of the job requirements or inadequate training.

An important reason for low morale is the poor leadership qualities of the immediate superior. Research on leadership in the Canadian workforce reported by Psychometrics Canada (2010) showed that poor leadership had negative effects on employees' morale. The study further advised that leaders -

- should talk less and listen more,
- should be more effective in addressing issues of morale,
- establish clear expectations,
- clearly communicate how the organization plan to manage change,
- assign tasks to staff based on skills instead of office politics,
- have a more informal interaction with staff,
- give employees more responsibility,
- hold people accountable,
- overcome resistance to change and
- defer to people with great expertise.

One can agree with the study conducted by Psychometrics Canada by adding further that some of the leadership skills that are important in enhancing the morale of employees are the ability to deal with change, good communication, set

goals and solve problems, manage people well (Schuler, 2004, Psychometrics Canada, 2010).

Stevens (2009) indicated that organizational change and culture both also impacted lower productivity and employee morale. According to Stevens (2009), other factors leading to low morale included leaders not serving as role-models, little or no accountability, too many silos and departmental infighting, lack of career and succession planning. White and White (2009) agreed with Stevens's factors and claimed further that leadership culture of control and command and weighed heavily against employee morale. Poor interpersonal relations, distrust of management, and inflexible working conditions could also adversely affect employees' morale (Dye & Garman, 2006). Workforce Performance Solutions (2006) further outlined that labor negotiations, departmental closures, high employee turnover rates, contract disputes, unclear expectations, changes in leadership, and corporate directions could also lead to employees' low morale.

March and Simon (1999) emphasized a correlation between morale and productivity, but Perrow (1986) disagreed by suggesting that the two are not necessarily related, even though common sense would seem to indicate that as one goes up, the other too would also go up. It is quite evident from the literature that the morale of employees was very important in the organization, and if it was not managed effectively, it could have adverse effects on the overall performance of the organization and productivity (Mazin, 2010, DPSA, 2006).

Measures to put in place to avoid low morale in the work environment

Kaczmarczyk and Murtough (2002) indicated that there are measures that employers may put in place to arrest the low morale of employees at the workplace. Those measures are enlisted below -

Job enlargement

Rotate employees so that they will not feel demoralized. Employees should be rotated regularly to various departments and hence learning new skills pertaining to those departments.

Providing good working conditions

Good working conditions included the employee's safety, provision of health services, regulation of working hours, a proper wage policy, and welfare services. All these helped in creating interest in the jobs among the employees.

Praising employees

If employees are praised sincerely by their seniors about their job performance, it leads to a sense of belonging and importance and boosts their morale.

Autonomy

Employees should be given autonomy in their jobs. Freedom at work makes them employees perform their work with confidence.

Proper treatment of employees

If managers or/and supervisors continuously poke their noses in the employees' work, they may have a negative attitude. Managers should not abuse employees as this reduces their respect, which in turn results in low morale.

Financial and non-financial incentives

When employees are assured of given benefits, job security, a social status recognized and credited for the task done; then they have satisfaction with their work, leading to high morale.

Employees participation in management

This is one of the most effective ways of eliminating negative attitudes towards their work and making employees work better. It creates a sense of belonging and confidence.

Solving grievances of employees'

If the management shows genuine concern while dealing with employees' grievances, then low morale will be minimized.

Fair promotion of employees

If employees are fairly promoted without any bias and prejudice, it positively impacts the morale with a positive attitude towards their organization and the job.

Factors leading to high morale

Topchik (2003), Ewton (2007), and Stevens (2009) identified factors that could lead to the promotion of good morale in the organization, and these researchers have mentioned that they are all aligned well with the principles of leadership.

These factors are discussed below.

Objectives of the Organization

If the employees consider the organizational goals important and useful, morale tends to be high.

Leadership

Another important factor in morale-building is the effectiveness of a manager in providing a satisfactory work environment. There is a positive impact on morale when the leadership enables the subordinates to achieve their aspirations and goals.

Group Members

High morale also results from the behavior and nature and of co-workers in the group. Cooperative members of the workgroup with mutual understanding and faith can lead to higher morale.

Job Satisfaction

The tasks assigned to employees are discharged well if they take pride in it and derive personal satisfaction from their work. Satisfying jobs results in high morale, especially when the employees have an opportunity for self-development.

Structure of organization

The organizational structure states the hierarchy of superior-subordinate relations. Suppose the responsibility and authority are clearly defined, and there is frank and free communication between the subordinates and superior. In that case, the situation is quite conducive to the building of high morale.

Monetary compensation and rewards

Reasonably satisfactory levels of salaries and wages, as well as a fair system of incentives and rewards for higher efficiency, are quite essential for employee satisfaction; thus, the morale is found to be higher when fair rewards and compensation were assured.

Advancement and promotional opportunity

Ambitious people highly prefer an organization that provides ample opportunities for advancement in their career through promotion for capable employees. The possibility of promotion to higher remuneration and responsibility is a positive factor that leads to high morale among employees.

Working Environment

Conditions at the workplace have a direct impact on the morale of the employees. Health care, provision for safety, and welfare of employees help build up their morale.

ANALYSIS AND CONCLUSION

Researchers have written widely on the concept of employee morale. This leads us to conclude that the concept remains significant. Notwithstanding the abstract nature of the term, researchers world-over have written on morale and its different dimensions. Studies carried by Indian authors are relatively much less. Morale and its dimensions like its importance, consequences, and causes of low morale, measures to avoid low morale, how to ensure high morale, and others always remain relevant for both academicians and practitioners alike. Given the dynamic nature of morale and the ever-increasing volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity in the variables affecting businesses, extensive research in the area is required.

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